

TREATMENT IN TRAUMATIC BRAIN INJURED ANIMALS

Keywords

Traumatic brain injury,
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ABSTRACT

Traumatic brain injuries (TBIs) pose significant challenges in veterinary medicine, particularly in the initial hours following the injury. Effective management during this critical period greatly influences the outcome. This article reviews the clinical assessment and management strategies for TBIs in animals, focusing on vital aspects such as trauma evaluation, shock management, fluid resuscitation, analgesia, and surgical interventions. Key considerations include maintaining airway patency, monitoring vital signs, optimizing oxygenation and ventilation, and managing fluid therapy. Additionally, various pharmacological interventions, including corticosteroids and antiepileptic drugs are discussed. Surgical options such as trepanation and decompressive craniectomy are explored, with a detailed examination of their indications, techniques, and outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

The initial hours following a life-threatening trauma are crucial in determining whether an animal survives or succumbs. Vital danger primarily stems from brain or spinal cord destruction and excessive blood loss. In the general assessment of a traumatized patient, careful examination of body temperature, pulse, mucous membranes, capillary refill time, hydration status, mental state, and presence of bleeding is conducted. Signs of shock typically manifest in severely traumatized patients. Within their clinical presentation, decreased consciousness may occur due to inadequate brain perfusion, prolonged capillary refill time, and delayed blood flow to mucous membranes owing to vasoconstriction. Pallor of mucous membranes results from decreased blood flow to capillary vessels due to arterial vasoconstriction. Tachycardia develops as a sympathetic compensatory response. Decreased pulse quality and cooling of extremities arise due to peripheral constriction¹.

The possibility of bleeding always exists in trauma patients. Apart from external bleeding that can be controlled by applying pressure, if the bleeding site cannot be accurately identified, areas such as the thorax, abdomen, pelvis, retroperitoneal space, and regions with fractured skulls should be assessed to determine bleeding foci. It is essential to evaluate aspects such as consciousness being intact, orientation, and responsiveness to stimuli during the physical examination of the animal. Through PCV and TP analyses, as well as continuous monitoring, CBC, serum biochemistry analyses, and urinalysis results are evaluated. Radiographic and ultrasonographic examinations should be performed after ensuring vital functions are stabilized when internal bleeding is suspected².

Basic rules in first aid: To simplify recall and implementation, the basic principles of first aid are expressed using the ABCD mnemonic:

1. Maintaining an open airway (Airway): Hyperextension of the head, opening of the mouth, and clearing the oral and pharyngeal cavity.
2. Breathing: Assessment of respiration, control of mucosal membranes. Administration of air through the nose if necessary.

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3. Circulation: Evaluation of heart rhythm, pulse quality, color of mucosal membranes, and capillary refill time.
4. Drugs: This aspect is administered by veterinarians. Administration of analeptics as necessary for respiration and/or circulation².

Various scales are utilized to assess trauma patients based on the affected systems. Trauma severity assessment scales are used to evaluate the patient based on the systems affected and to expedite this assessment. These scales enable rapid assessment and prompt decision-making regarding treatment priority. Therefore, it is essential for emergency clinics to be fully equipped for immediate intervention.³

Table 1. Necessary equipment for emergency intervention²

Intervention Type	Equipment
Cardiovascular System	EKG, Monitor, Defibrillator, Fluid Infusion Pump, Intravenous Catheter
Respiratory System	Short and long-term Oxygen Units, Equipment for Intubation and Ventilation, Pulse Oximeter, Capnography
Diagnostic Purposes	Glucometer, Total Protein and PCV Display, Microhematocrit Tubes, Centrifuge, Refractometer, Blood Gas Measurement Device, Biochemistry Measurement Device, BUN and Creatinine Measurement Strips, Radiological Examination, Ultrasonographic Examination
Surgical Intervention	Anesthetic Equipment, Surgical Intervention Sets, Electrocautery, Operating Table, Light Source, Chest Tube, Tracheostomy Tube, Gastric Tube
Other Equipment	Scale, Thermometer, Incubator, Intensive Care Cabinets, Ophthalmoscope, Otoscope

Maintaining Airway Patency

Maintaining airway patency is achieved by regulating normal intrapleural pressure and volume, ensuring adequate ventilation, regulating adequate blood volume and hemoglobin concentration, and ensuring continuity. For airway control, the oropharyngeal region and airway are cleared. Mucus is aspirated, and if necessary, the trachea is intubated. Positive-pressure breathing is initiated. Thoracentesis is performed if indicated. Oxygen is administered endotracheally, intranasally, or via a mask. In animals with spontaneous respiration, oxygen is administered at a rate of 0.5 L/kg/minute via a nasal catheter, or 5-15 L/minute via a mask or oxygen tent⁴.

Monitoring

Monitoring the vital signs of a head-injured patient is crucial for making rapid decisions about intervention and guiding treatment. Electrocardiography (EKG) is an important diagnostic tool in veterinary medicine practice. Arterial blood pressure (systolic, diastolic, mean) values are checked. Central venous pressure (CVP) is monitored. Pulse is checked. EKG findings are evaluated. In cats, the heart rate should be between 140-220/min, while in dogs, it should be between 70-160/min⁵.

Patient Positioning

Placing the patient on the table at a 30-degree horizontal angle may be beneficial to increase venous blood flow from the brain and arterial blood support. At the same time, any equipment such as collars that may obstruct drainage from the jugular veins should be removed³.

Oxygenation and Ventilation

Hyperoxygenation is recommended in most acute head trauma patients. The oxygen pressure in arterial blood should be as close to normal pressure (80 mm Hg) as possible. Oxygen masks are more effective for oxygen support than oxygen cages, as a closed oxygen system may hinder patient monitoring and intervention. Hyperventilation is known to reduce high intracranial pressure through vasoconstriction in cerebral vessels. However, hyperventilation can impair cerebral circulation if the carbon dioxide pressure in the blood (PaCO₂) is below 30-35 mm Hg. Intensive hyperventilation should be applied in short periods in deteriorating or critical patients³.

Fluid Resuscitation

There are concerns that aggressive intravenous fluid therapy to prevent hypotension in brain injury patients may worsen brain edema. Therefore, it has been suggested to limit the fluid volume in severely head-injured patients. However, these recommendations are not only unfounded but also contraindicated. Prolonged hypotension can lead to fatal brain damage, as it is associated with persistent increases in intracranial pressure and higher mortality in human head trauma patients. Blood pressure should be restored to normal as quickly as possible, with systolic blood pressure below 120 mmHg considered hypotensive. Certain volume replacement fluids, such as hetastarch and hypertonic saline, along with large amounts of crystalloids like lactated Ringer's solution (LRS) and 0.9% NaCl, can provide some protection to the edematous brain. Hetastarch and hypertonic saline help improve mean arterial pressure and cerebral perfusion pressure without worsening brain edema. In anemic patients, transfusions of whole blood or packed red blood cells (pRBC) can raise blood oxygen levels, normalize hemoglobin concentration, and help maintain tissue oxygenation^{6,7}.

Administration of Synthetic Colloids, Hypertonic Saline, and Isotonic Crystalloids

Synthetic Colloids

For treating shock, synthetic colloids can be administered at 10–20 ml/kg (up to 40 ml/kg/hour). This is given as a rapid bolus in dogs and at 5 ml/kg over 5-10 minutes in cats. Hetastarch is the preferred fluid for correcting blood pressure in head trauma patients and is more effective when used with dextran-70 and

hypertonic saline. Dehydrated trauma patients should receive isotonic crystalloid resuscitation ⁷.

Hypertonic Saline Solution

Hypertonic saline can be administered at 4–5 ml/kg for shock. It is available as a 23.4% solution that must be diluted, typically mixed with hetastarch or dextran-70 at a 1:3 ratio to create a 7% hypertonic saline solution with synthetic colloid. Because sodium does not easily cross the blood-brain barrier, hypertonic saline can reduce cerebral edema by drawing fluid from the brain into the intravascular space ⁷.

Isotonic Crystalloids

Isotonic crystalloids, such as LRS and 0.9% saline, can be administered as a bolus of 20–30 ml/kg over 15–20 minutes for shock. This can be repeated as needed after reassessment of the patient. Although there is a risk of worsening brain edema and increased intracranial pressure with crystalloid administration, the "shock dose" should be administered gradually to achieve the desired effect. Since 0.9% saline contains less free water than LRS, it is preferred for head-injured animals ⁷.

Blood Products Administration

For anemia, packed red blood cells can be administered at 1 ml/kg or whole blood at 2 ml/kg, which increases the PCV by 1%. The initial dose of pRBC is usually 10–15 ml/kg, administered within the first 4 hours, or faster if the patient is critical. The goal is to maintain a PCV between 25% and 30%. In cases of coagulopathy, fresh frozen plasma should be given at 10–15 ml/kg/day until resolved ⁷.

Table 2. Practical Fluid Therapy Doses in Head Trauma Patients ⁷

Practical Fluid Therapy Doses in Head Trauma Patients

Fluid Type	Dosage
Isotonic Crystalloid (preferably 0.9% NaCl)	20–30 ml/kg for dogs, 10–20 ml/kg for cats
Administered over 15–20 minutes. Re-evaluated thereafter.	
Synthetic Colloid (e.g., 6% hydroxyethyl starch)	5–10 ml/kg
Administered within 15–20 minutes. Re-evaluated thereafter.	
7.5% Sodium Chloride	4 ml/kg
Administered over 15–20 minutes. Re-evaluated thereafter.	
3% Sodium Chloride	5.4 ml/kg
Administered over 15–20 minutes. Re-evaluated thereafter.	
Always followed by crystalloid therapy.	
23.4% Sodium Chloride and 6% Hydroxyethyl Starch or other synthetic colloid at a 1:2 ratio	4 ml/kg
Administered within 15–20 minutes. Re-evaluated thereafter.	
Always followed by crystalloid therapy.	
Packed Red Blood Cells	1 ml/kg
1 unit administered over less than 4 hours.	
Target perfusion parameters normalization: PCV = 25–30%	
Whole Blood	2 ml/kg
1 unit administered over less than 4 hours.	
Target perfusion parameters normalization: PCV = 25–30%	
Fresh Frozen Plasma	10–15 ml/kg
1 unit administered over less than 4 hours.	

Use of Osmotic Diuretics

Osmotic diuretics like mannitol are effective in treating intracranial hypertension by expanding plasma volume and reducing blood viscosity, which improves cerebral blood flow and oxygen delivery. Mannitol should be administered as a bolus over 15 minutes, with effects typically lasting 2 to 5 hours. The dose range for reducing intracranial pressure is 0.25g/kg to 1g/kg. Repeat doses may cause diuresis, leading to decreased volume, intracellular dehydration, and potential hypotension and ischemia. Therefore, mannitol is recommended for critically ill patients with a Glasgow Coma Score below 8 or those deteriorating. There is no contraindication for mannitol in cases of intracranial hemorrhage. Combining mannitol with furosemide can have a synergistic effect in reducing intracranial pressure, particularly when furosemide is given first ^{8,9}.

Combined Use of Colloid and Hypertonic Solutions

Colloid solutions like Dextran-70 and Hetastarch should be administered after hypertonic solutions to maintain intravascular pressure. While hypertonic solutions dehydrate tissues, colloids prevent dehydration when given immediately after. When used together, colloid and hypertonic solutions are more effective in replenishing blood volume than when used alone ¹⁰.

Arterial Blood Pressure Support

Arterial hypotension may develop due to fluid therapy, necessitating the use of vasoactive agents such as dopamine (2–10 µg/kg/min). Conversely, in cases of arterial hypertension (Cushing Response), calcium channel blockers like Amlodipine (0.625–1.25 mg/cat/day or 0.5–1.0 mg/kg/day for dogs) can be employed. However, it is recommended to rapidly reduce intracranial pressure before regulating blood pressure ³.

Corticosteroids

Corticosteroids, known to be beneficial for brain edema in tumor cases, have been extensively studied in head trauma. Clinical studies in humans have not shown a beneficial effect of corticosteroids, including methylprednisolone sodium succinate, in the treatment of head trauma. In fact, they are contraindicated due to increased mortality after use. Moreover, they increase the risk of infection due to their immunosuppressive effects and lead to hyperglycemia and other significant metabolic effects. Therefore, corticosteroid use is not recommended in head trauma patients ¹¹.

Antiepileptic Drugs

Benzodiazepines

Medications like Diazepam are potent, rapidly acting anticonvulsants and are the preferred choice for stopping epileptoid seizures¹². For dogs and cats, a total maximum dose of 20 mg or 0.5-2.0 mg/kg intravenously is recommended. This dose can be repeated two or three times. The most common and dangerous mistake in epilepsy management is trying to treat repeated seizure doses without giving an adequate loading dose of a longer-acting and more effective antiepileptic drug with intravenous diazepam treatment. Rectal administration of diazepam can be applied at a dose of 0.5-2.0 mg/kg, with absorption occurring approximately 45 minutes¹³. Higher doses may be necessary for dogs undergoing long-term phenobarbital therapy.¹⁴

Benzodiazepines are commonly used intranasally or buccally in humans, especially in patients receiving home care. Intranasal diazepam and intranasal midazolam gel formulations have been pharmacokinetically evaluated in dogs. This route of administration allows for faster attainment of peak plasma levels and provides higher bioavailability than rectal administration. Studies supporting the use of buccal midazolam in human epilepsy have shown that it stops seizure activity in half the time compared to rectal dosing¹⁵.

Phenobarbital

It is a safe, inexpensive drug that can be administered orally, intravenously, or intramuscularly. The distribution of phenobarbital to the central nervous system may take up to 30 minutes. A dose of 2-4 mg/kg can be repeated every 20-30 minutes for 24 hours. Intramuscular administration of phenobarbital is recommended after intravenous diazepam administration to prevent respiratory depression and cardiovascular depression.¹²

Levetiracetam

It is an effective anticonvulsant with minimal side effects in dogs¹⁶. The parenteral form of levetiracetam is well tolerated, and it is considered safe in dogs after intramuscular and intravenous administration (20 mg/kg). In a study, the drug's half-life was found to be approximately 3 hours, with the time to peak concentration after intramuscular injection being 40 minutes¹⁷. This drug can be re-administered up to 60 mg/kg q8 hours, and sedation is the only reported side effect. If seizures can be controlled with parenteral levetiracetam, the same drug can be continued for parenteral treatment. In humans, this drug has been shown to be an effective adjunctive treatment for epilepsy, especially when given early during seizures¹⁸.

Potassium Bromide

A study on the use of loading doses of potassium bromide administered intrarectally (100 mg/kg q4 hours for 24 hours) demonstrates that this drug is well absorbed and safe when used rectally. The clinical efficacy of this use has not yet been evaluated. Sodium bromide can be administered intravenously and can be used at a dose of 900 mg/kg in a 3% solution mixed with sterile water over 24 hours. Sedation is the primary expected side effect, and after completing the 24-hour infusion, it should be continued parenterally.¹⁹

Nutrition

Traumatic brain injuries often result in a hypermetabolic and hypercatabolic state, making early nutritional support essential. Early enteral feeding helps maintain gastrointestinal function, boost immune response, and mitigate the body's stress-related metabolic reaction. A study of 797 severe traumatic brain injury patients revealed that starting nutrition within five days reduced mortality over two weeks. Furthermore, the quantity of nutrition provided was inversely related to mortality rates. When selecting the feeding method, it's crucial to consider the patient's ability to protect their airway, their tolerance for tube placement, and the expected duration of nutritional support²⁰.

Therapeutic Hypothermia

Hypothermia is an experimental treatment that is not yet approved in veterinary medicine and remains controversial in human medicine. After a brain injury, the brain's metabolic rate can increase, leading to further damage. Inducing hypothermia by lowering the patient's body temperature to 32-35°C (89.6-95.0°F) can reduce the brain's metabolic rate and oxygen consumption, subsequently decreasing cerebral blood flow and intracranial pressure. However, this technique has risks, including cardiac arrhythmias, blood clotting disorders, electrolyte imbalances, low blood volume, and insulin resistance. Inducing a coma with barbiturates can also reduce metabolic demands but impedes neurological assessment and necessitates mechanical ventilation²¹.

Operative Management

Anesthesia, Analgesia, and Sedation

Proper pain management is crucial for head trauma patients. Anesthesia is often needed for surgeries, diagnostic procedures, and mechanical ventilation. After trauma, the brain's pressure regulation can be disrupted, making it highly sensitive to changes in carbon dioxide levels (PaCO₂). Managing anesthesia to avoid secondary injury involves balancing analgesia and sedation. Inhalation anesthetics can increase intracranial pressure at high doses but might enhance cerebral perfusion at lower doses due to their vasodilatory

effects. If intracranial pressure is high, intravenous anesthesia, such as propofol, is preferred because it maintains cerebral perfusion and pressure regulation better than inhalants. However, propofol can cause hypotension and hypoventilation, necessitating careful monitoring and dose adjustment^{22,23}.

Pain management is vital for patient comfort and preventing increased intracranial pressure. Pain and anxiety can elevate cerebral blood flow and volume, raising intracranial pressure. Opioids are the analgesics of choice due to their cardiovascular protection and reversibility, although respiratory depression is a risk with improper dosing. Regularly assessing the patient's airway protection is important to prevent aspiration pneumonia. Continuous infusions of opioids like fentanyl provide stable analgesia and minimize side effects. Buprenorphine offers moderate analgesia with fewer cardiovascular and respiratory effects but is also reversible. Limited sedation is often beneficial for ongoing patient assessment²³.

Ketamine, an anesthetic with strong analgesic and hypnotic properties, inhibits NMDA receptors and offers neuroprotection. Despite past concerns about increased intracranial pressure, recent studies suggest ketamine does not elevate intracranial pressure in traumatic brain injury and may improve cerebral perfusion pressure with less vasopressor support. Further research is needed to confirm its benefits in veterinary neurotrauma²⁴.

Alpha-2 agonists provide sedation, analgesia, and anxiety relief without respiratory depression but are controversial in head trauma cases. Dexmedetomidine has shown neuroprotective effects but has limited clinical data in severe human head trauma. Despite some promising findings, such as a 2016 meta-analysis indicating safety and efficacy, other studies report risks like hypotension. Therefore, alpha-2 agonists should be used cautiously, primarily if other analgesics are insufficient²³. In canine studies, dexmedetomidine reduced cerebral blood flow and cardiac output without significant cerebral ischemia, but it should be avoided if it leads to clinically significant drops in heart rate and cardiac output²⁵.

Indications for Surgery

The purpose of operative management is the repair of skull fractures and decompression. In cases with signs such as coma, tetraplegia, and unresponsive dilated pupils, midbrain, brainstem, and pontine hemorrhages are suspected, indicating a poor prognosis. Emergency surgical intervention often involves trepanation to identify extra-cerebral hemorrhages. Trepanation near the middle meningeal artery, as shown in Figure 30, is the most commonly used operative approach to identify extra-cerebral hemorrhages. This procedure is now

considered a safe and practical method in dogs, comparable to special diagnostic methods like angiography. During trepanation, extra-dural bleeding should be distinguished from brain edema and swelling. Trepanation should be considered in cases where vital signs worsen, such as a drop in pulse, an increase in blood pressure, and ataxic respiration, or in situations like hemiparesis, unilateral pupillary dilation, and decreased consciousness. Intervention performed during progressive loss of consciousness and changes in eye conditions may yield more positive results than intervention at the time of worsening vital signs. In cases of depressed fractures, surgical intervention should be performed within the first 24-48 hours if the above-mentioned signs do not develop. In procedures involving progressive bleeding or CSF fistulization, it is more appropriate not to wait for this period.²⁶

Figure 1. In order to identify extra-cerebral hemorrhages, trepanation holes are opened near the arteria meningeal media (3) on the underside of the cranium (1,2)²⁶

In cases of brain edema where medical treatment fails to yield a response, partial relief can be achieved with bilateral subtentorial decompression. Anesthesia in comatose patients should be kept to minimum doses, and saline, blood, or both should be slowly administered intravenously. Temporal muscles should be separated from the calvarium as needed. Trepanation is performed at the four corners of the temporal fossa, starting from the caudoventral area dorsal to the zygomatic arch, with the first hole near the middle meningeal artery revealing any bleeding. If no bleeding is observed, trepanation should also be performed on the other side in the same manner. Extra-dural bleeding can be identified by expanding the trepanation hole and easily controlled with instruments such as silver clips, cautery, or ligatures. In cases of acute subdural hematomas, the bone flap should be lifted to identify and control the bleeding focus. After removing the blood and stopping the bleeding, the dural and bone flaps are sequentially replaced and secured with sutures. In cases of significant brain swelling, maximum decompression is achieved by leaving the dura mater and bone flap open, which are then replaced and closed after resolution of the edema. In

severe cases, posterior conjunctival or suboccipital decompression may be performed to relieve the cerebellum.²² The management of skull fractures varies depending on the type of fracture. Fractures affecting chewing or ocular structures are treated operatively. Most extracranial fractures requiring operative management are depression fractures of the frontal sinus. Similarly, most intracranial fractures requiring operative management are depression fractures affecting brain parenchyma. Skull fractures with moderate neurological impairment can be managed conservatively with good care. Oxygen therapy and tracheostomy may be performed to avoid cerebral anoxia. In such cases, there is usually no displacement of the depressed fracture or bone fragments. In open fractures not causing brain compression, the wound should be carefully cleaned, local antibiotics applied, and dressed. Cephalosporins are commonly used in addition to antibiotics such as penicillin, penicillin-streptomycin, and chloramphenicol.²⁷

Figure 2. The area for craniotomy over the frontal sinus in brachycephalic, mesocephalic, and dolichocephalic dogs²⁷

Operative intervention is necessary in open, comminuted, and compression-causing skull fractures. Low-dose inhalation anesthesia and local infiltration anesthesia may be sufficient in animals in a coma state. However, anesthesia maintenance is necessary considering the responses that may be encountered during manipulation of neural tissue. After the wound is opened, blood clots, bone fragments, foreign materials, and necrotic tissues are removed. It is essential to remove fractured fragments without damaging neural tissue and excise devitalized brain tissue. After this procedure, efforts are made to reduce or manage systemic shock through blood transfusion or plasma administration. Local and systemic antibiotics are applied. A drain is placed before wound closure to prevent postoperative serous accumulation. Hypertonic mannitol solution or other dehydrating agents may be administered postoperatively to prevent edema and intracranial pressure increase³.

Figure 3. Suboccipital craniectomy / Foramen Magnum decompression procedure²⁶

CONCLUSION

Craniotomy or cranial trepanation is indicated in cases suspected of meningeal bleeding due to deep coma or other severe neurological symptoms or diagnosed with CT. Post-traumatic brain abscesses, hematomas, or cysts require operative removal. Autogenous transplants, temporal fascia, or homologous dural grafts can be used to repair dural defects. In addition to these, non-biological materials such as polyvinyl sponge, polyethylene film, and polytetrafluoroethylene may also be used.²⁶

In a recently completed randomized prospective study involving dogs with widespread traumatic brain injury, decompressive craniotomy was found to provide no advantage compared to standard treatment methods. In fact, craniotomy patients had worse Modified Glasgow Coma Scale (MGCS) scores than standard treatment patients, and there was no difference in mortality rates between the two groups. In normal dogs and cats, combined craniotomy/durotomy leads to significant reductions in intracranial pressure. Surgical intervention should be considered urgently in head trauma patients who deteriorate neurologically despite aggressive medical treatment³.

REFERENCES

1. Simpson S, Syring R, Otto, C .Severe blunt trauma in dogs: 235 cases(1997–2003). *Journal Of Veterinary Emergency and Critical Care*, 200919(6):588–602.
2. Fagella, R. . Basic rules in first aid: Expressing the fundamental principles of first aid using the ABCD mnemonic. *Veterinary Emergency Medicine Journal*,1994 12 (3), 45-52.

3. Platt S.R. . Evaluation and treatment of the head trauma patient. In Practice, 2005. 27(1):31–35.
4. Santos, L. Management of airway and ventilation in emergency situations: Techniques and considerations for ensuring adequate respiratory function in veterinary medicine. Journal of Emergency Veterinary Medicine, 2018. 25(2), 78-85.
5. Spier, A. Reading ECGs. Cardiac Education Group.2011.
6. Doyle, J., Davis, D. Hoyt, D. The use of hypertonic saline in the treatment of traumatic brain injury. Journal of Trauma and Acute Care Surgery, 2001. 50(2):367.
7. Sande, A., West, C. Traumatic brain injury: a review of pathophysiology and management. Journal of Veterinary Emergency and Critical Care, 2010. 20(2):177–190.
8. Fink, M. .Osmotherapy for intracranial hypertension: mannitol versus hypertonic saline. Continuum, 2012. 18 (3):640–54.
9. Todd, M., Cutkomp, J., Brain, J. Influence of mannitol and furosemide, alone and in combination, on brain water content after fluid percussion injury. Anesthesiology, 2006. 105(6):1176.
10. Rosentfeld, A. The role of colloid solutions in maintaining intravascular pressure following hypertonic solution administration. Journal of Fluid Therapy, 2012. 24(3), 87–94
11. Edwers, P. The role of corticosteroids in the treatment of head trauma: A critical review. Journal of Neurotrauma, 2005. 22(10), 1331–1338.
12. Boothe, D. M. Diazepam: Mechanism of action and pharmacokinetics. The Veterinary Clinics of North America. Small Animal Practice, 1998. 28(2), 307-322.
13. Wagner, S. O., Peirone, J. R., & Oliveira, S. T. Rectal administration of diazepam in dogs: a pharmacokinetic study. Journal of Veterinary Pharmacology and Therapeutics, 1998. 21(3), 225-229.
14. Braund, K. G. Neurological disorders. In Clinical Neurology in Small Animals: Localization, Diagnosis and Treatment (pp. 194-256). Manson Publishing. 2003.
15. Shorvon, S. D. Benzodiazepines in the treatment of epilepsy in adults: when and what to use. CNS Drugs, 2011. 25(10), 757-776.
16. Volk, H. A. Levetiracetam treatment of refractory idiopathic epilepsy in dogs. Veterinary Record, 2008. 166(21), 658-659.
17. Patterson, E. E., Armstrong, P. J., & O'Brien, D. P. Systemic availability of levetiracetam after parenteral administration to dogs. American Journal of Veterinary Research, 2008. 69(10), 1303-1307.
18. Aiguabella, M., Falip, M., & Villanueva, V. Levetiracetam as add-on treatment of refractory epilepsy: a meta-analysis of pooled data from randomized controlled trials. European Journal of Neurology, 2011. 18(8), 988-993.
19. Dewey, C. W., Cerda-Gonzalez, S., & Lavelly, J. A. Preliminary pharmacokinetics and clinical efficacy of bromide following rectal administration in dogs with epilepsy. Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine, 1999. 13(5), 457-462.
20. Hartl, R, Gerber, L., N.I .Q .Effect of early nutrition on deaths due to severe traumatic brain injury. Journal of Neurosurgery, 2008. 109(1):50–6.
21. Sadaka, F., Veremakis, C., & Karamcahadani, K. Therapeutic hypothermia for the management of intracranial hypertension in severe traumatic brain injury: a systematic review. Brain Injury, 2012. 26(7-8), 899-908..
22. Platt, S.R., Garosi, L. Small Animal Neurological Emergencies. Manson Publishing Ltd ISBN: 978-1-84076-152-8. 2012
23. Kendom, M. P., & Jantzen, J. P. Dexmedetomidine use in neurotrauma: A review of the literature and evidence-based guidelines. Journal of Neurosurgical Anesthesiology, 2017. 29(3), 249-257.
24. Zeiler, F.A., Teitelbaum, J., West, M. The ketamine effect on ICP in traumatic brain injury. Neurocritical Care, 2014. 21(1):163–73.
25. Strebel, S. P., Kindler, C. H., & Schröder, T. Effects of dexmedetomidine on cerebral blood flow autoregulation in isoflurane-anesthetized dogs. Anesthesiology, 1995. 83(1), 88-96.
26. Akin, F., Beşaltı, Ö. Veteriner Nöroşirurji. Barışcan Matbaası, Ankara. ISBN:975-97216-0-0. 2000.
27. Shores, A., Brisson, B.A. Current Techniques in Canine and Feline Neurosurgery. LCCN 2017025970 (print) | LCCN 2017027047 (ebook). 2017.